

Calibration of the mixing length of the MLT and FST models using 3D hydrodynamical models

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Abstract

Rich spectra of solar-like oscillations obtained with space observations are expected to enable us to perform precise determinations of stellar properties. To make the best of the spectra, we need theoretical stellar models with precise near-surface structure, since the near-surface structure has significant influence on solar-like oscillation frequencies. The mixing-length parameter, α , is a key factor to determine the near-surface structure. We aimed at determining appropriate α values based on 3D radiation-coupled hydrodynamical models produced by the CO⁵BOLD code. For such calibration, previous works concentrated on the classical mixing-length theory (MLT). Here we also analyzed the full spectrum turbulence (FST) models. The trends of the calibrated α values in the $T_{\text{eff}}-g$ plane is found to be similar to those of previous calibrations with the other grids of RHD models. A $T(\tau)$ relation based on the so-called VAL-C solar-atmosphere model is found to give better correspondence to the photospheric-minimum entropy in the 3D model than the Eddington $T(\tau)$ relation. Although the structure below the photosphere depends on convection models, not a single convection model gives the best correspondence to the 3D model since physical quantities in the 3D models are not necessarily related via an equation of states unlike those in the 1D models. Although the FST model with a form of a mixing length $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$ is found to give solar-oscillation frequencies apparently closest to the observed ones, the acoustic cavity of this model is formed with compensatory effects between deviating density and temperature profiles just below the top of the convective envelope. In future work, a more sophisticated treatment of the top part of the 1D convective envelope is necessary.

1 Introduction

The recent spacecraft missions such as CoRoT and *Kepler*/K2 provided a wealth of high-quality data. It would enable us to perform asteroseismic studies with unprecedented quality. The forthcoming PLATO mission is expected to provide a wealth of seismic data for an even larger set of bright stars. Rich spectra of stellar oscillations can lead to tight constraints on stellar global parameters such as age, mass and radius and properties of the interior structure. However, this requires theoretical stellar models that have comparable quality than the observed data.

For solar-like oscillations, the so-called surface effects prevent us from obtaining correct theoretical frequencies. These effects occur due to an incorrect modeling of the near-surface layers, which is mainly caused by too approximate a determination of the temperature gradient in the superadiabatic layers. The classical mixing-length theory (MLT) proposed by Böhm-Vitense (1958, hereafter BV) has been commonly used for modeling of convection in stellar evolution codes. The assumption of a single size of convection eddies is not preferable to model near-surface turbulence. In addition, it is required to give values of several free parameters included in the adopted convection formulation. The most prominent free parameter is the mixing length, defined as $l = \alpha H_p$, where H_p is the pressure scale height, and α a free parameter. The arbitrariness of the α value is problematic, and a physically-grounded constraint is required.

On the other hand, radiation-coupled hydrodynamical (RHD) simulations have successfully produced realistic profiles of the near-surface turbulence. Using results of such simulations, Steffen (1993) carried out a calibration of the α

value based on a 2D-RHD solar model. Ludwig *et al.* (1999, hereafter LFS) and Freytag *et al.* (1999) extended the calibration to different solar-like stars. Trampedach *et al.* (1997) had carried out the calibration based on 3D-RHD models, which was recently updated by Trampedach *et al.* (2014) using an increased number of 3D models introduced by Trampedach *et al.* (2013). Ludwig *et al.* (2008) performed the calibration based on 3D models made by the CO⁵BOLD code (Freytag *et al.*, 2002; Wedemeyer *et al.*, 2004; Freytag *et al.*, 2012), and Magic *et al.* (2015) followed with 3D models by the STAGGER code (Magic *et al.*, 2013). Compared to the 2D models, the 3D models are likely to give higher α values due to more efficient convection. The calibrations based on RHD models have shown that the α value for the standard MLT becomes lower as the effective temperature increases or the surface gravity decreases. In such calibrations, different treatments of atmosphere parts in calibrated 1D models have caused quite a bit of conflicting results among the different previous works. Nevertheless, such calibrations would provide us with physically guaranteed values of α .

For 1D computations of stellar evolution, the full spectrum turbulence (FST) models were proposed by Canuto & Mazzitelli (1991) and Canuto *et al.* (1996, hereafter CGM). While the MLT assumes a single size of convection eddies, the FST model takes into account contribution of different size eddies based on the Eddy Damped Quasi-Normal Markovian model. In spite of the improvement in describing convective fluxes, the FST model adopts an incompressible turbulence model. As a result, a distance scale does not appear naturally. In addition, even if one chooses the distance to the convection boundary as adopted in Canuto & Mazzitelli (1991), it is not

able to fit the solar radius with accuracy required for seismic studies. Hence, an ad-hoc free parameter for the scale distance must be introduced to compensate for other uncertainties in stellar physics and get such precision. Previously the calibration with the FST model has been carried out only based on 2D-RHD models (LFS; Freytag *et al.* 1999). As it has been shown that the α value substantially differs between 2D and 3D models for MLT, it is worth investigating the α values of the FST model also based on 3D models.

In the present work, we carried out the calibration by matching standard 1D envelope models with 3D-RHD models produced by the CO⁵BOLD code. The number of the models was increased compared to Ludwig *et al.* (2008), and a wide range of the effective temperature and surface gravity is covered.

2 Theoretical models

2.1 3D atmosphere models

We adopted 25 3D-RHD models with the solar metallicity from the CIFIST grid (Ludwig *et al.*, 2009), which was produced by the CO⁵BOLD code. This code solves the time-dependent equations of compressible hydrodynamics coupled to radiative transfer in a constant gravity field in a Cartesian computational domain, which is representative of a volume located at the stellar surface. The equation of state takes into account the ionization of hydrogen and helium as well as the formation of H₂ molecules according to Saha-Boltzmann statistics following Wolf (1983). We adopted the multi-group opacities based on monochromatic opacities stemming from the MARCS stellar atmosphere package (Gustafsson *et al.*, 2008). For the calculation of the opacity with the MARCS package, the chemical abundance basically follows the solar mixture by Grevesse & Sauval (1998). For the CNO elements, we followed Asplund (2005).

In the RHD simulation, a specific entropy value is given to convective up-flows entering from the bottom of a simulation box. We define this entropy value as $s_{3D,bot}$. Namely, $s_{3D,bot}$ is an input parameter, while the effective temperature is not. Since the up-flows are adiabatic, their entropy values are determined by $s_{3D,bot}$ until reaching the vicinity of the photosphere. By its nature, $s_{3D,bot}$ can be regarded as the asymptotic entropy value in the adiabatic limit of the bottom of a convective envelope, s_{asy} . And it was used as a constraint for the α calibration (Steffen, 1993).

On the other hand, down-flows experience significant heat exchange in the superadiabatic layers just below the photosphere, and hence their entropy values are certainly lower than the asymptotic value in the bottom part of the convective envelope, and they reduce the horizontally averaged value. Some of our 3D models are not deep enough for their averaged entropy values to reach the asymptotic values at the bottoms of the simulation boxes. Therefore, it would be preferable to adopt the asymptotic value to constrain 1D envelope models.

2.2 1D envelope models

Calibration of the mixing-length parameter α for the MLT and FST models was carried out by matching the entropy value at the adiabatic bottom part of convective envelopes in 1D models with the asymptotic entropy of the 3D models. To do so, we produced 1D envelope models using a shooting code developed by LFS, which proceeds integration from atmosphere surface without boundary conditions imposed at a stellar center. Same as the CO⁵BOLD code, the equation of state follows Wolf (1983), and the opacity is based on

the MARCS package (Gustafsson *et al.*, 2008). Although the MARCS package provides opacity for different wavelength bands, which have been adopted to the CO⁵BOLD 3D simulations, a gray Rosseland-mean version was adopted to the 1D models, while the same chemical abundance as the 3D models was adopted. In the present work, turbulent pressure was not included in the 1D models following common practice in stellar structure models. Hence, our calibrated α values should be used for evolutionary computation without turbulent pressure, while they include information of turbulent pressure in the 3D models.

In order to model convection in 1D envelope models, we adopted the convective fluxes from the CGM formulation, and those from an MLT formulation proposed by Böhm-Vitense (1958). In previous α calibrations with RHD models, the Böhm-Vitense (1958) version was adopted by LFS and Trampedach *et al.* (2013), while Magic *et al.* (2015) adopted another version proposed by Henyey *et al.* (1965).

It is necessary to evaluate the radiative temperature gradient ∇_{rad} for use of the Schwarzschild criterion and of the convection models in a convective region. In a radiative region, the radiative temperature gradient represents the actual temperature gradient. In the present work, the radiative temperature gradient is defined as

$$\nabla_{rad} \equiv \left(\frac{d \ln T}{d \ln p_g} \right)_{rad} = \frac{3}{16\sigma} \frac{\kappa F_{tot} p_g}{g T^4} \left(1 + \frac{dq(\tau)}{d\tau} \right) \quad (1)$$

where σ denotes the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, κ the Rosseland-mean opacity per unit mass, F_{tot} total (radiative plus convective) flux, p_g gas pressure, g gravitational acceleration, T temperature. τ is the optical depth, determined by $d\tau \equiv -\kappa \rho dr$, where r denotes radius and ρ density. $q(\tau)$ is a Hopf function, given by a $T(\tau)$ (temperature-optical depth) relation for radiative equilibrium. In the optically thin limit, Eq. (1) satisfies the differentiation of

$$\frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{T}{T_{eff}} \right)^4 = \tau + q(\tau) \quad (2)$$

where T_{eff} denotes the effective temperature. Toward optically thicker layers, Eq. (1) approaches the diffusion approximation since $dq/d\tau \rightarrow 0$ ($\tau \rightarrow \infty$).

An entropy profile significantly depends on a $T(\tau)$ relation. In previous α calibrations, LFS and Trampedach *et al.* (2014) used $T(\tau)$ relations derived from their RHD models. On the other hand, Magic *et al.* (2015) used a 1D atmosphere code (Magic *et al.*, 2013) which solves radiative transfer by itself.

In the present work, we adopted fixed $T(\tau)$ relations which can be easily implemented into 1D stellar evolution codes. The first one is the Eddington gray $T(\tau)$ relation ($q(\tau) = 2/3$), which has been commonly implemented in many stellar evolution codes. Another one is a $T(\tau)$ relation with the solar-calibrated Hopf function (J. Christensen-Dalsgaard, private communication),

$$q(\tau) = 1.036 - 0.3134e^{-2.448\tau} - 0.2959e^{-30.0\tau}, \quad (3)$$

which is based on Model C of Vernazza *et al.* (1981, VAL-C). Model C was derived by solving non-LTE radiative transfer, statistical equilibrium of atomic levels and hydrostatic equilibrium so that a spectrum matches with one obtained by the *Skylab* observation of the quiet Sun.

For the integration of 1D envelopes, aside from the chemical abundance, we need three global parameters, effective temperature T_{eff} , surface gravity acceleration g and stellar total mass M . Although we input 3D values for T_{eff} and g ,

Figure 1: Entropy profiles as function of total pressure for the solar model. The thick gray line is the temporally and horizontally averaged entropy in the 3D model, and the thin blue lines are those in the 1D models with different values of the mixing-length parameter α , which are indicated near the blue lines. For the 1D models shown here, CGM and the VAL-C $T(\tau)$ relation were used. The horizontal dashed red line indicates the asymptotic entropy of the 3D model, s_{asy} .

we set M to $1M_{\odot}$ for all the models, which is justified by small sensitivity of α to M .

3 Calibration of mixing-length parameter α

3.1 Method

We calibrated values of the mixing-length parameter α for the 25 3D models with the solar abundance. Figure 1 shows the α calibration for the solar 3D model adopting an FST model proposed by CGM and VAL-C $T(\tau)$ relation to the corresponding 1D model. The entropy decreases toward the interior in the radiative part of the atmosphere, while it increases in the convective region, which begins near the photosphere. While the gray thick line is the temporally and horizontally averaged profile of the 3D model, the blue thin lines are those of the 1D model with different α values.

As α increases, the entropy jump between the top of the convective envelope and the adiabatic interior decreases. By a bisection method, we searched for an appropriate α value, which makes the entropy value at the 1D bottom close to the 3D asymptotic entropy, s_{asy} , which is indicated as the horizontal dashed red line in Fig. 1.

3.2 Solar α values

Table 1 shows the calibrated α values for the solar model. As for MLT, we here show results with the version of Böhm-Vitense (1958). α has a different meaning among the frameworks of the different convection models. For CGM, mixing length is defined as $l = \alpha H_p$. However, unlike for MLT, this α value is smaller than one (see also Canuto, 1996). CGM2 uses the mixing length introduced in the CGM paper: $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$. The subscript “top” refers to values at the top of the convective envelope. The last term introduces a correction with respect to the distance to the convective boundary, and it can be interpreted as a kind of overshooting above the convection boundary. The corresponding parameter α^* is expected hence to be much smaller than the α

Table 1: Calibrated α values for the solar model.

	VAL-C	Eddington
MLT	2.051	1.780
CGM	0.821	0.702
CGM2	0.355	0.216

values appearing in the other convection models. Moreover, the influence on the temperature gradient of varying α^* is much smaller than that of varying α in CGM and MLT.

The α values of MLT and CGM are similar to those provided by previous empirical calibrations. Adopting the Eddington $T(\tau)$ relation, Samadi *et al.* (2006) reported $\alpha = 1.76$ for MLT and $\alpha = 0.69$ for CGM. Our calibrated α values (1.780 and 0.702 for MLT and CGM, respectively) are in good agreement with them. Salari & Cassisi (2015) calibrated not only for the Eddington $T(\tau)$ but also for VAL-C with MLT. They reported $\alpha = 1.69$ for the Eddington $T(\tau)$ and 1.90 for VAL-C. Although these α values are ~ 0.1 smaller than our values, they showed that VAL-C results in a certainly larger α value than the Eddington $T(\tau)$ similarly to our result.

3.3 Calibrated 1D model profiles

3.3.1 Equilibrium structure

Figure 2 compares the 1D entropy profiles with different convection models and $T(\tau)$ relations for the solar model. For the 1D models, the entropy profile in the radiative part of the atmosphere depends on $T(\tau)$ relations, while the convective inner part depends on convection models.

Dependence on $T(\tau)$ relations

The VAL-C $T(\tau)$ generally gives better agreement of the photospheric-minimum entropy with the 3D profile than the Eddington $T(\tau)$. The Eddington $T(\tau)$ commonly results in a smaller photospheric minimum and hence larger entropy jump. The entropy jump is firmly associated with the α value. Indeed, Magic *et al.* (2015) showed certain inverse correlation between α values and entropy jumps. While the top of an entropy jump is determined by the asymptotic entropy, which stems from a 3D model, the bottom of the jump, namely the photospheric-minimum entropy, depends on the $T(\tau)$ relation. Due to the larger entropy jump, the Eddington $T(\tau)$ relation generally gives a smaller α value than VAL-C $T(\tau)$.

Dependence on convection models

Below the photosphere, a 1D profile depends on the convection model. Figure 2 shows that the CGM model with $l = \alpha H_p$ has a steeper entropy gradient than MLT. Canuto (1996) showed that the MLT overestimates the convective flux for low-efficiency convection, while underestimates for high-efficiency convection. Hence, MLT requires a smaller temperature gradient in the superadiabatic layers, and a higher gradient in the adiabatic bottom layers (Fig. 3). While the growth of small eddies is suppressed by radiation in the low-efficiency convection, different size eddies contribute to energy transport in the high-efficiency convection. The CGM model reflects this tendency, but the single-eddy-size approximation that MLT adopts misses it.

CGM2 has an even steeper entropy gradient. Hence the entropy approaches the asymptotic value more quickly if we compare at the same-pressure location. By the definition $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$, the mixing length becomes smaller

Figure 2: Same as Fig. 1, but for the calibrated 1D models with different convection models and $T(\tau)$ relations. While the mixing length is determined as $l = \alpha H_p$ for MLT and CGM, $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$, where the subscript “top” means the top of the convective envelope, for CGM2.

as going upward. Indeed, the convective flux has high sensitivity to the mixing length ($F_{\text{conv}} \propto l^8$, see e.g. Gough & Weiss, 1976) in the low efficiency limit. To compensate for this, the gradients of temperature and hence entropy should become steeper (Figs. 2 and 3). Since the mixing length increases substantially with depth, the contrast of the entropy gradient is extreme between the bottom and top of a convective zone.

While nonlocal effects are included in the 3D models, the 1D models were produced with a local treatment. This treatment forces the convective velocity to be zero at the Schwarzschild boundary. Just below the top of a convective envelope, therefore, the convective velocity has an extremely steep gradient. It causes a pronounced density inversion as well as steep temperature gradient. Due to the smaller convective flux for low-efficiency convection, the CGM model has steeper temperature gradient (Fig. 3) and hence larger density inversion (Fig. 4). On the other hand, 3D models have no density inversion.

The correspondence between 1D and 3D models significantly depends on physical quantities to be compared. For example, while the entropy profile with CGM matches best with that of the 3D model as function of pressure (Fig. 2), the MLT model is closer to the 3D model in terms of the temperature (Fig. 3). The averaged thermodynamic quantities of the 3D model are not related via an EOS particularly in the convection zone where horizontal fluctuations are large. In contrast, they are related in 1D models. Hence it is hard to pursue the complete correspondence of all the quantities at the same time.

3.3.2 Oscillation frequencies

Although we address the difficulty in the comparison of the equilibrium structure among the 3D models and the calibrated 1D models in Sect. 3.3.1, comparing oscillation frequencies could shed light on such an issue particularly from the viewpoint of asteroseismology. To obtain appropriate frequencies, we combined the solar 1D and 3D envelope models with a 1D interior model constructed by the CESTAM stellar evolution code (Marques *et al.*, 2013). The in-

Figure 3: Same as Fig. 2, but for the temperature profiles of the solar 3D model and calibrated 1D models having different convection models with VAL-C. The horizontal gray line indicates the effective temperature.

Figure 4: Same as Fig. 3, but for the density profiles.

terior model is similar to the one produced by Sonoi *et al.* (2015, 2017), but it was updated so that the frequencies of the radial low-order modes in the resulting patched model match better with the observed ones provided by Broomhall *et al.* (2009). We chose a CESTAM model having the solar mass, an age 4.99 Gyr, MLT with $\alpha = 1.651$, and Eddington $T(\tau)$ atmosphere, and no turbulent pressure. We then replaced the outer part of this model with the solar 1D and 3D envelopes.

Next, we computed adiabatic radial-mode frequencies of the resulting patched models using the ADIPLS code (Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2008). For the 3D model, which includes turbulent pressure, we computed frequencies adopting the reduced-gamma model (RGM) and gas-gamma model (GGM) approximations (Rosenthal *et al.*, 1999). While RGM neglects the Lagrangian perturbation of turbulent pressure, GGM assumes that the relative Lagrangian perturbation of turbulent pressure is equal to that of gas pressure. To take into account the perturbation of turbulent pressure in a more physically-grounded way, the 3D-model frequencies were also computed using the MAD code (Dupret *et al.*, 2002) with

Figure 5: Difference between adiabatic radial-mode frequencies of the solar patched models with the 3D and calibrated 1D envelope models and the observed ones provided by Broomhall *et al.* (2009) as function of the observed frequency. The error bars stem from the observed frequencies.

a time-dependent treatment of convection (TDC) for adiabatic oscillations introduced by Sonoi *et al.* (2017) based on the formalism by Grigahcène *et al.* (2005) and Dupret *et al.* (2006).

Figure 5 shows the difference between the patched model frequencies and the observed ones provided by Broomhall *et al.* (2009). As for the TDC frequencies of the 3D model, the TDC formalism has a free parameter β related to the closure problem. In this figure, we show TDC frequencies with $\beta = -0.44 - 0.34i$, which was found to give frequencies close to the observed ones. Among the 1D-envelope-patched models, the frequencies for CGM2 with VAL-C $T(\tau)$ are found to result in the lowest frequencies, which are eventually closest to the observed frequencies. CGM follows it, and MLT gives the most deviating frequencies. We also see that the Eddington $T(\tau)$ gives higher frequencies than VAL-C.

However, we must be aware that CGM2 has a much steeper temperature gradient and much stronger density inversion around the superadiabatic layers than the other convection models (Fig. 2, 3 and 4). Namely, their apparently appropriate frequencies are coming about by compensatory effects between such deviating density and temperature profiles.

To solve the problem of the compensatory effects, the 1D models might need a larger acoustic cavity with moderate gradients of thermodynamical quantities by taking into account additional physics such as turbulent pressure and overshooting so that they have as low frequencies as the RGM frequencies of the 3D model without the perturbation of turbulent pressure. As for the effects of this perturbation, for now, we can see them by comparing the 3D frequencies of RGM, GGM and TDC. If we compare RGM and GGM, we see that the inclusion of this perturbation even in a crude way should increase the frequencies. The result with TDC shows that the more sophisticated method can bring the frequencies closer to the observed ones.

Figure 6: Calibrated α values (dots) and fitting function (Eq. 4, contour) for CGM with the VAL-C $T(\tau)$ in the $T_{\text{eff}} - \log g$ plane. The solar model is labeled as the solar mark.

3.4 Trends of calibrated α among different stellar models

In case of the mixing length $l = \alpha H_p$ (MLT and CGM), the calibrated α value becomes generally larger with decreasing T_{eff} or increasing g since the entropy jump becomes smaller, which means that the convection becomes more efficient. This tendency has been also found by previous calibrations with RHD models (LFS; Trampedach *et al.*, 2014; Magic *et al.*, 2015).

In case of another mixing length $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$ (CGM2), the α^* value becomes larger with increasing T_{eff} or g . This tendency is consistent with LFS. As mentioned in Sect. 3.2, the meaning of α^* is different from the case of $l = \alpha H_p$, and may be interpreted as a kind of overshooting above a convective envelope. For a few low- T_{eff} models, the calibrated α^* values are found to be negative. These negative values are required to make entropy jumps high enough to obtain the asymptotic entropy matching. A negative α^* value leads to a negative mixing length l just below the top of the convective envelope. In the present work, we assumed purely radiative transfer in the layers with negative l .

We performed functional fitting to the α values of all the models we investigated. Similarly to LFS and Magic *et al.* (2015), we fitted a function

$$f(x, y) = a_0 + (a_1 + (a_3 + a_5x + a_6y)x + a_4y)x + a_2y \quad (4)$$

to the α values with a least-squares minimization method, where $x \equiv (T_{\text{eff}} - 5777)/1000$ and $y \equiv \log g - 4.44$. Namely, x and y represent deviations from the solar effective temperature and surface gravity, respectively. As an example, the resulting fitting function for CGM with the VAL-C $T(\tau)$ is shown as the contour in Fig. 6. Resulting values of the coefficients a_i for all the combinations of the convection models and $T(\tau)$ relations are shown in Table 2. The last two columns show the deviation of the fitting function from the calibrated α values. The first one is the root-mean-square deviation $\Delta_{\text{rms}} = \sqrt{\sum_i^N (f_i - \alpha_i)^2 / N}$, where N is the number of models, and the second one is the maximum of the absolute deviation, $\Delta_{\text{max}} = \max(|f_i - \alpha_i|)$. They are smaller for CGM than CGM2 and MLT. Namely, Eq. (4) works better for CGM than CGM2 and MLT.

Table 2: Resulting values of the coefficients a_i of the fitting function f (Eq. 4) to the calibrated α values, and the root-mean-square and maximal deviation of the fits from the calibrated α , Δ_{rms} and Δ_{max} .

Conv.	$T(\tau)$	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	Δ_{rms}	Δ_{max}
CGM	VAL-C	0.821021	-0.062016	0.110100	0.018825	-0.029943	-0.009310	-0.006214	0.010	0.020
	Eddington	0.703031	-0.103263	0.087566	0.021193	-0.023523	0.029304	-0.019150	0.008	0.017
CGM2	VAL-C	0.359522	-0.118199	0.061132	0.009828	-0.122208	0.168391	-0.124905	0.040	0.109
	Eddington	0.225285	-0.138345	0.030226	-0.023650	-0.065260	0.257248	-0.117526	0.037	0.077
MLT	VAL-C	2.057349	-0.047880	0.107147	-0.009432	-0.011211	-0.039115	0.012995	0.018	0.039
	Eddington	1.790295	-0.149542	0.069574	-0.008292	0.013165	0.080333	-0.033066	0.025	0.067

Figure 7: Same as Fig. 6, but for CGM2 with VAL-C.

3.5 Impacts on stellar evolution

We tested evolutionary computation of a $1M_{\odot}$ star with varying α which follows Eq. (4) using the code ATON 3.1 (Ventura *et al.*, 2008). Figure 8 shows evolutionary tracks with the α values calibrated for MLT and CGM with the Eddington $T(\tau)$. The dashed lines are tracks with α fixed to the solar value (Table 1), and the solid lines are those with varying α which follows Eq. (4). The varying- α tracks for the different convection models (and $T(\tau)$ relations) should be identical to each other since they are based on the same grid of the 3D models. In practice, they commonly have $T_{\text{eff}} \simeq 4100$ K at $\log g = 2$, but they are not exactly identical due to the uncertainty on the interpolation of the calibrated α in the sparse grid of the 3D models. As shown in the last two columns of Table 2, the deviation of the fitting function $f(x, y)$ from the calibrated α ranges from ~ 0.01 to ~ 0.1 depending on the convection models and $T(\tau)$ relations.

Figure 9 shows the variation of the α values on the evolutionary tracks with varying α . The difference in the tracks appears mainly in the low- T_{eff} side due to the deviation of the calibrated α values from the solar value.

For MLT, the difference between the tracks with the solar α and the varying α is much smaller than for CGM. Some recent papers have also found such a small difference for MLT. Using the 3D-calibrated α values for MLT given by Trampedach *et al.* (2014), Salaris & Cassisi (2015) and Mosumgaard *et al.* (2018) computed evolution with varying α . For $1M_{\odot}$ star evolution, Salaris & Cassisi (2015) reported that the RGB track hardly differs between the cases of the solar α and varying α when the 3D-calibrated $T(\tau)$ relation (Trampedach *et al.*, 2013) was used for both the cases. Rather they found larger shifts of the RGB track by up to 100 K when comparing the varying- α track with the 3D $T(\tau)$ relation and

Figure 8: $1M_{\odot}$ evolutionary tracks obtained with the α values calibrated with the Eddington $T(\tau)$ relation. The solid lines are tracks with varying α which follows Eq. (4). The dashed lines are ones with α fixed to the solar values (Table 1).

tracks with some fixed $T(\tau)$ relations and α value fixed to 1.76, the solar value given by Trampedach *et al.* (2014).

Mosumgaard *et al.* (2018) also reported that a T_{eff} shift from a solar- α track with the Eddington $T(\tau)$ to a varying- α track with the 3D $T(\tau)$ relation (Trampedach *et al.*, 2013) is not substantial, $\sim +30$ K at $\log g = 3.2$ for $1M_{\odot}$. We find it similar to the T_{eff} shift from our solar- α to varying- α track for MLT, which is $\sim +24$ K at the same $\log g$.

For CGM, the T_{eff} shift from the solar- α to varying- α track in the upper part of the RGB tracks is much larger than for MLT. The shift is found to be $\simeq 40$ K at $\log g = 3$ and $\simeq 120$ K at $\log g = 2$. Such a larger T_{eff} shift can be explained by the larger deviation of the varying α value from the solar value as shown in Fig. 9.

4 Summary

We calibrated the mixing-length parameters of the mixing-length theory (MLT) and full spectrum turbulence (FST) model based on 3D radiation-coupled hydrodynamical models produced by the CO⁵BOLD code. For the FST model, we performed additional calibrations using a mixing length of the form $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$ in addition to $l = \alpha H_p$.

In each case, we investigated with two outer conditions: the Eddington gray $T(\tau)$ relation and the one with the solar-calibrated Hopf-like function based on Model C of Vernazza *et al.* (1981, VAL-C). The VAL-C $T(\tau)$ is found to give better correspondence to the 3D photospheric-minimum entropy than the Eddington $T(\tau)$ independently of convection

Figure 9: Variation of α on the evolutionary tracks shown in Fig. 8. The horizontal dashed lines indicate the solar values shown in Table 1.

models, since the energy transfer is totally radiative in the atmosphere part except the vicinity of the photosphere.

On the other hand, the structure below the photosphere depends on convection models. The FST model makes a steeper entropy gradient than MLT. The definition of a mixing length $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$ gives a much steeper gradient than $l = \alpha H_p$, which agrees with a result shown by the Canuto, Goldman & Mazzitelli (1996) paper.

It is found that not a single convection model gives the best correspondence to a 3D model in a convection zone. For example, while the FST model with $l = \alpha H_p$ gives the best correspondence to the 3D entropy profile, it does not necessarily give the best correspondence to the 3D temperature profile and MLT comparably gives better correspondence. Unlike 1D models, averaged 3D quantities are not necessarily related via an EOS due to the convective fluctuation. Hence, it is hard to pursue the complete correspondence of all the quantities at the same time. We compared radial-mode frequencies of the solar models to which the 3D envelope and the calibrated 1D envelope models are patched. The FST model with $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$ gives the frequencies closest to the observed ones. In the 1D models, however, the local treatment forces the convective velocity to have extremely steep gradient just below the top of the convective envelope. It leads to a density inversion in the 1D models while the 3D models do not have it. The apparently appropriate frequencies of the FST with $l = r_{\text{top}} - r + \alpha^* H_{p,\text{top}}$ are caused by the compensatory effects between the deviating density and temperature profiles. It implies that the inclusion of additional physics such as turbulent pressure and overshooting might be required.

We tested evolutionary computation with varying α based on our 3D-calibrated values. For MLT, the change from the solar α to the varying α hardly shifts the evolutionary track, which is consistent with the other papers. For FST, on the other hand, the shift is found to be much larger particularly in the red giant phase.

Although VAL-C $T(\tau)$ is found to give good correspondence to the photospheric-minimum entropy of 3D models, we stress that we limited the present work to $T_{\text{eff}} \gtrsim 4500$ K for $\log g \gtrsim 2.5$. For lower T_{eff} , H_2 formation is important for a temperature profile in atmosphere, and a more appropriate $T(\tau)$ relation should be required.

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